

Tools for defining a fair price and strengthening crop diversification value chains

Problem

Introducing new crops into cropping systems involves experimenting, investing and taking risks for farmers. If they do not receive additional value for new crops compared to more common crops, it may discourage crop diversification.

Similarly, the processing and marketing of new products resulting from crop diversification requires downstream actors to innovate, which in turn requires additional resources.

Solution

When encouraging farmers to undertake crop diversification, the price of the new crops should provide additional value compared to more common crops.

Value chains must also ensure a fair distribution of benefits among actors, in consistency with their risks and investment levels.

A list of 14 criteria for defining a fair price for new crops and value chains was developed. A related questionnaire helps actors discuss the price level and matters such as value repartition, transparency, etc.

Benefits

A special attention to pricing is needed at the innovation stage of crop diversification. When good pricing levels are proposed, crop diversification can take place more easily. A fair pricing process can strengthen actors' capacity for innovating and creating sustainable and fair value chains.

Practical recommendation

- By going through the **list of fair pricing criteria (Figure 1)**, farmers and other value chain actors can get an overview of the concept of a fair price.
- This list constitutes a collection of potential conditions which contribute to fair pricing mechanisms. Actors can **choose the most relevant criteria** for their project. As fairness is highly context-dependent, different criteria might be more or less important for different projects.
- The relative importance of criteria is also likely to change as the project grows and evolves. Pricing and fairness should be discussed and reviewed regularly.
- The related **questionnaire** can allow actors to assess the current status of pricing in their value chain, and to identify which fair pricing criteria are the most important and relevant for the future of their project, both individually and collectively.

Example

The DiverIMPACTS Belgian case study aiming to support *intercropping grain legumes with cereals in organic systems (CS18)* used the fair pricing criteria list in order to foster discussion on the value repartition within their value chains and establish fair, long-term relations between value chain actors.

Applicability box

Theme

Value chain, actors, learning, assessment

Agronomic conditions

n/a

Application time

Any

Required time

Minimum 2 hours

Period of impact

Immediate

Equipment

n/a

Best in

Value chains with direct interactions between actors and a collaborative mindset.

Figure 1: List of the 14 criteria for defining a fair price (Anton Riera, UCLouvain).

1 - Production and market criteria	
1. A fair price is usually higher than a minimum price.	Considering reference prices (e.g. market price, competing products' prices, etc.) can contribute to evaluating and setting a fair price.
2. A fair price should cover the production costs.	Estimating production costs and integrating them in the price definition is a way to ensure a fair price. This implies considerations in terms of: scope of included costs; transparency; and governance.
3. A fair price should allow for a good revenue level.	Ensuring that farmers get a good revenue level can contribute to achieving a fair price. This requires a reflection on the quantity of labour needed and on what is a fair level of revenue.
4. Consideration for the added value compared to other crops.	When farmers undertake crop diversification, taking the opportunity cost (i.e. a comparison against the reference crop which would otherwise be grown) into account might contribute to setting a fair price.
5. A fair price should be acceptable to consumers.	The acceptability and affordability for consumers should be taken into account when setting a price, for example by estimating the consumers' willingness to pay.
2 - Chain development criteria	
6. A fair price should allow for investments.	Ensuring that further investments are possible might contribute to fair prices. The relevance of investments should be evaluated against a reference cost and depending on the context of the project.
7. Risk sharing and premium for innovation or risk-taking.	Accounting for innovations and risk-taking might contribute to a fair price (e.g. through a premium for innovation). This entails considerations on how the risks are shared and how the level of the premium is defined.
8. Stability and/or reassessment of the price.	How is the evolution of the price over time defined? What triggers price reassessments? Ideally, the reassessment mechanisms, which are specific to each project, should be transparent.
3 - Relationship between actors	
9. Transparency principles.	Transparency within the value chain relates to several aspects: value repartition, production costs (which ones are covered), and governance mechanisms (who is involved in the decision-making processes).
10. Fair value distribution.	A fair distribution of value and profit among actors can contribute to fair pricing mechanisms. This requires considerations on the mechanisms which define a fair distribution (e.g. based on workload, capital, etc.).
11. Long-term commitment of actors.	A long term commitment of actors can contribute to fair pricing mechanisms. The relationship between producers and buyers/processors must be clearly defined to ensure stability, even in bad years.
12. Shared effort by all actors to guarantee commercial outlets.	Mutual, bilateral relations can be important for fair pricing mechanisms. This involves a commitment of all actors to maintain the chain, communication and a common understanding of needs and expectations.
13. Fair governance mechanisms.	This relates to the way decision-making mechanisms are put in place (e.g. who has a say? are decisions made unilaterally?). It applies to price setting and all decisions in general (e.g. quality, payment times, etc.).
14. Payment in a fair time.	This relates to two aspects: a minimum delay between the delivery of the primary product and the payment; a possibility to provide (total or partial) pre-payment if necessary.

Further information

- Download the related questionnaire: <https://sytra.be/publication/fair-price-tools/>

About this practice abstract and DiverIMPACTS

Publisher:
UCLouvain

Authors: Riera Anton, Antier Clémentine

Permalink: <https://zenodo.org/record/5913250>

This practice abstract was elaborated in the DiverIMPACTS project, based on the EIP AGRI practice abstract format. It was tested in three innovative value chains in Belgium (DiverIMPACTS Case Study 18).

DiverIMPACTS: The project is running from June 2017 to May 2022.

The overall goal of DiverIMPACTS - Diversification through Rotation, Intercropping, Multiple Cropping, Promoted with Actors and value-Chains towards Sustainability - is to achieve the full potential of diversification of cropping systems for improved productivity, delivery of ecosystem services and resource-efficient and sustainable value chains.

Project website: www.diverimpacts.net

© 2022

The project DiverIMPACTS - "Diversification through Rotation, Intercropping, Multiple Cropping, Promoted with Actors and value-Chains towards Sustainability" is supported by the European Union's HORIZON 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement no 727482 and by the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (SERI) under contract number 17.00092. The opinions expressed and arguments employed herein do not necessarily reflect the official views of the EC and the Swiss government. Neither the European Commission/SERI nor any person acting behalf of the Commission/SERI is responsible for the use which might be made of the information provided in this practice abstract. The authors and editors do not assume responsibility or liability for any possible factual inaccuracies or damage resulting from the application of the recommendations in this practice abstract.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 727482 (DiverIMPACTS)

Swiss Confederation

Federal Department of Economic Affairs,
Education and Research EAER
State Secretariat for Education,
Research and Innovation SERI